

5th International Marine and Fisheries Symposium

Faculty of Marine Science and Fisheries **&** Institute of Tropical Aquaculture and Fisheries - Akwatrop
UNIVERSITAS HASANUDDIN & Universiti Malaysia Terengganu

*"Advancing Marine and Fisheries Sectors to Achieve the
Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)
for Healthy Aquatic Environment and Society"*

05 JUNE 2022

ABSTRACT BOOK

RUANG SALISSINGAN : Aquatic Ecology and Conservation; Aquatic Biodiversity
Moderator : Associate Prof. Dr Liew Hon Jung

Abstract Code	GMT (+8)	Title	Presenter	Preferred Attendance
OPENING by Moderator (13.30 – 13.35)				
ABS-287	13.30-14.30	Application of morphological characterization and molecular identification to resolve species ambiguity: A UMT experience	Nur Asma Ariffin -	Online
ABS-013		Capture-based aquaculture of glass eel nurseries, <i>Anguilla bicolor</i> in Cilacap, Central Java, Indonesia	Purnama Sukardi	Online
ABS-058		Population status and microhabitat preferences of endemic Banggai cardinalfish (<i>Pterapogon kauderni</i>) in the introduced habitat in Kendari Bay, Indonesia	Ucu Yanu Arbi	Online
ABS-059		Production of Triploid Catfish <i>Clarias</i> sp by Heat-shock Chromosome Set Manipulation	Ainina Ahmad Rozy	Offline
ABS-061		Status of <i>Barbodes binotatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1842) in Ecological Trophy in the Ciliwung River Region, West Java	Gema Wahyudewantoro	Online
ABS-076	14.30-15.30	The Possibility of Replacing Corn Meal with Coconut Waste on the Growth Performance of African catfish (<i>Clarias gariepinus</i>)	Muhammad Fikri Abdul Hadi	Offline
ABS-096		Length-weight Relationship and Condition Factor of Seven Fish Species from Apogonidae Family in Lembah Strait, North Sulawesi	Fione Yukita Yalindua	Online
ABS-112		The unrevealed of water quality parameters at Lake Oemasapoka, Rote island - investigation the concentration of heavy metal in a saline environment	Luki Subehi	Online
ABS-116		Mangroves in Southeast Aru Marine Protected Area	Nur Mujid Abdullah	Online
ABS-124		Sea grass Morphological Characters in Islands with Different Distance from the Mainland	khairul amri	Offline
BREAK SESSION (15.30-15.45)				
ABS-208	15.45-16.35	Disappearance or Overlooked or Untouched? - A Brief History of Aquatic Gastropoda of Malaysian Borneo	Abdulla-Al-Asif	Online
ABS-212		Turf Algae Dynamics in the Coral Reef Ecosystems of the Spermonde Archipelago	Gunawan Syafruddin	Online
ABS-219		Diversity and abundance of Intertidal Biota in front of Shrimp Ponds on Lombok and Sumbawa Island	Edwin Jefri	Online
ABS-234		Conditions of megabenthos on coral reef ecosystem in Seribu Islands National Park, Jakarta	Dedy Kumiawan	Offline
ABS-251	16.35-17.25	Megabenthos Monitoring in Ternate, North Maluku	Putri Sapira Ibrahim	Online
ABS-267		Occurrence of ectoparasites on Nile Tilapia (<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>) from South Sulawesi Lakes, and Aquaculture facility	Hilal Anshary	Online
ABS-271		Mapping of Sea Urchins as a Potential Resource in the Wallacea Region: a Preliminary Review	Wilma Moka	Offline
ABS-281		The Effect Of Fermentation Time And Different Raw Materials On N And P Content As Nutrient Sources Of <i>Caulerpa</i> Sp. Organic	Murni Mardani	Offline
Best Presenter Announcement and Closing				

[ABS-208] (144)
**Disappearance or Overlooked or Untouched? - A Brief History of Aquatic
Gastropoda of Malaysian Borneo**

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Abstract

The aquatic Gastropoda (marine and freshwater) in Malaysian Borneo (MYB) has an ancient history of 255 years, while the first record was observed in 1767 by the pioneer Carl Linnaeus. With time, many European, native taxonomists and conservationists worked on the diverse group of Gastropoda in the Malaysian part of Borneo (states of Sabah and Sarawak). No previous work was conducted to assess the historical existence of this particular class of Mollusca. The study's objective was to reveal the types of aquatic gastropods in MYB and the number of published research and expeditions conducted herein. The bibliometric analysis suggested that 145 research publications mentioned the names of the region where they reported at least one species from this geographic region. Within the history of 255 years, a total of 559 species of gastropod were reported by the different research groups. Between 1767 and 1900, a total of 150 gastropod species were reported, followed by 79 species from 1900 to 2000 and 330 species from the year 2001 to 2022. The Grubbs test ($p < 0.05$) suggested that the most outlier year in reporting of species was 2011, while it recorded 54 new species from MYB, followed by 2020 (54 species), 2001 (39 species). The most contributing taxonomist in MYB within the history of aquatic gastropod research was Han Raven and his colleagues from NBC, The Netherlands, who reported 111 new species from the region followed by Nur Leena Wong from UPM (54 new species). The finding suggested that reporting of new species from MYB is increasing, which can be interpreted as the many unexplored new sites and species still exist in this ecoregion. In this regard more expedition works, and research dimensions might help to know the exact number of aquatic gastropod species in this area. This observation will help the regional governments in making the regional biodiversity database as well as to take decisions for research initiatives on aquatic gastropods and management.

Keywords: biodiversity; taxonomy; borneo; mollusca; natural history